

Do Brain-Inspired Spiking Neural Networks Outperform Other Deep Learning Models in EEG Seizure Prediction?

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Abstract

The development of robust seizure prediction models and devices is critical for advancing clinical applications in epilepsy care. In this study, we investigate whether biologically inspired Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs), which mimic neuronal firing mechanisms, offer advantages over conventional deep learning architectures for EEG-based seizure prediction. Using the CHB-MIT dataset, we systematically compare the performance of five models—LSTM, CNN, SNN, GNN, and Transformer—given the same preprocessing and training pipeline. These models are then trained on around 23 hours of CHB-MIT data and evaluated using accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and ROC AUC metrics. Our results show that SNNs delivered robust and consistent performance, achieving the higher accuracy, specificity, and ROC AUC scores than LSTM, CNN, and Transformer models, but comparable to GNNs. GNNs achieved the highest average sensitivity, a clinically critical metric. While SNNs demonstrated strong overall reliability and highlight the potential of brain-inspired architectures for advancing seizure prediction systems, they still require further refinement to surpass the best-performing conventional models.

Keywords: deep learning, neural networks, signal processing, EEG, seizure prediction

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Context

Neural signal processing

Neural signals are electrophysiological signals generated from the activity of neurons, which facilitate information transmission across the nervous system. They are often recorded using techniques such as electroencephalogram (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). These neural signals are characterized by high-dimensionality, nonstationarity, and noisiness. Because of this, they require techniques such as filtering, spectral analysis, and feature extraction to remove artifacts and obtain meaningful patterns and information [1, 2].

Neural signal processing is an interdisciplinary field focused on processing neural signals to understand how the brain represents and transmits information [3]. This includes acquisition, preprocessing, analysis, and interpretation of neural signals. It utilizes neural signals for a broad range of applications, including but not limited to:

- Neuroprosthetics & neurostimulators
- Brain-machine interfaces
- Monitoring & treatment of neurological disorders
- Computational neuroscience [4]

Recently, AI-based techniques have been employed to process neural signals, achieving great performance in applications such as seizure detection, movement intention decoding, and speech synthesis from neural activity [5]. This approach will be explored in this study.

Epilepsy & seizure prediction via EEG signals

Epilepsy is a neurological disorder that affects around 50 million people worldwide, characterized by epileptic seizures, which are periods of involuntary muscle contractions and convulsions as a result of excessive electrical discharges in the brain. People affected by epilepsy have more physical problems, psychological conditions, and have up to three times higher risk of premature death than the general population [6]. Prediction of epilepsy using EEG data involves learning and modeling complex, time-dependent neural activity patterns to forecast brain states.

Deep learning architectures offer a compelling direction for exploration and research. Their performance in complex, nonlinear data are well-suited for capturing and processing EEG signals. By advancing these architectures and the principles that they are built upon, we are able to develop practical healthcare applications.

1.2 Literature Review

Neural signal processing

Work done on neural signal processing utilizes both classical signal processing techniques and AI-based methods. Various filtering techniques, such as multi-channel Wiener filters (MWF), FIR/IIR filters, and Butterworth filters, are used to remove artifacts from noisy signals [7, 1]. Feature extraction methods are then used to extract valuable information from the signal. Wavelet transforms, empirical mode decomposition, and Fourier transform variants are used for frequency-domain and multi-resolution analysis [8, 9, 10]. Methods such as approximate entropy, fast Fourier transform (FFT), and discrete wavelet transforms (DWT) have also been utilized in biomedical neural signal processing systems, such as EEG seizure detection systems [11]. Neural signal processing pipelines can be built entirely on these classical signal processing techniques or incorporate machine learning and deep learning models down the pipeline. These models include convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [12], long short-term memory (LSTMs) [13], and transformers [14], which have demonstrated superior performance to traditional processing techniques across a wide range of neural signal processing tasks.

EEG seizure prediction

Many studies have been done on seizure prediction using EEG data and deep learning, with most of them framing the problem as a binary classification task with interictal and preictal periods as labels. Wu et al. [15], Tsiouris et al. [16], and Chambers et al. [17] aim to learn the temporal dependencies of neural activity in EEG signals and anticipate seizures by leveraging long short-term memory (LSTM) models. Building on this, Lee et al. [8], Liu et al. [18], and Bhattacharya [19] used variations of the LSTM model, namely the Resnet-LSTM, BiLSTM, and CNN-LSTM, to better capture complex bidirectional and spatio-temporal dependencies. Truong et al. [20], Khan et al. [21], and Usman et al. [22] used a convolutional neural network (CNN) model to model spatio-temporal dependencies in EEG signals, even eliminating the need for handcrafted feature extraction.

1.3 Problem Statement & Purpose

The purpose of this study is to explore whether brain-inspired Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) offer advantages over conventional deep learning architectures for seizure prediction. We formulated our question based on the fact that SNNs are explicitly designed to process information in a way that resembles how the brain encodes and transmits signals, making them a natural candidate for tasks involving neuronal activity, such as EEG-based seizure prediction. We compare five architectures—LSTM, CNN, SNN, GNN, and Transformer using the same preprocessing pipeline, allowing us to isolate the role of model design in performance differences.

Our objectives and contributions are summarized as follows:

- We provide a brief review of representative deep learning architectures used in EEG-based modeling.
- We conduct a controlled comparison of five architectures, including the brain-inspired SNN and four conventional models, on an EEG seizure prediction task.

While these models are trained and tested on EEG-based seizure prediction, they have not yet been deployed or validated in real-world clinical environments. Due to limited computational resources, evaluation was restricted to the first 7 patients in the CHB-MIT dataset, which may affect generalizability. Furthermore, the use of a preprocessing pipeline rather than raw EEG input introduces additional constraints. These limitations should be addressed in future work.

1.4 Methodology overview

We benchmark five deep learning architectures—LSTM, CNN, SNN, GNN, and Transformers—on an EEG-based seizure prediction task using the CHB-MIT dataset. EEG data were preprocessed, segmented, and labeled, with features extracted from spectral bands. Models' hyperparameters were tuned via a grid search and were trained using standard optimization techniques and evaluated via accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and ROC AUC metrics to assess performance in seizure prediction.

2 Methods

2.1 Overview of architectures

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

For an input sequence $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ at time t , the LSTM cell computes:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i) \quad (1)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (2)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o) \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_c x_t + U_c h_{t-1} + b_c) \quad (4)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t \quad (5)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (6)$$

Final output:

$$y = \sigma(W_2 \text{ReLU}(W_1 h_T + b_1) + b_2)$$

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

For input $x \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times L}$:

$$z = \text{ReLU}(\text{Conv1D}(x, W_c) + b_c) \quad (7)$$

$$p = \text{MaxPool}(z) \quad (8)$$

$$f = \text{Flatten}(p) \quad (9)$$

$$y = \sigma(W_2 \text{ReLU}(W_1 f + b_1) + b_2) \quad (10)$$

Spiking Neural Network (SNN)

For a Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) neuron:

$$u_t = \beta u_{t-1} + W x_t \quad (11)$$

$$s_t = H(u_t - \theta) \quad (12)$$

$$u_t = u_t \cdot (1 - s_t) \quad (13)$$

where β is the leak constant, θ is the firing threshold, and $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function. Final output after dense layers:

$$y = \sigma(W_3 \text{ReLU}(W_2 u_T + b_2) + b_3)$$

Graph Neural Network (GNN)

For a graph $G = (V, E)$ with node features $h_v^{(0)} = x_v$:

$$h_v^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\sum_{u \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_v d_u}} W^{(l)} h_u^{(l)} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$H_G = \frac{1}{|V|} \sum_{v \in V} h_v^{(L)} \quad (15)$$

Final output:

$$y = \sigma(W_2 \text{ReLU}(W_1 H_G + b_1) + b_2)$$

Transformer

For input sequence $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$:

$$Q = XW_Q, \quad K = XW_K, \quad V = XW_V \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (17)$$

$$H^{(l+1)} = \text{FFN}(\text{Attention}(Q, K, V)) \quad (18)$$

$$y = \sigma(W_2 \text{ReLU}(W_1 H_{[CLS]}^{(L)} + b_1) + b_2) \quad (19)$$

where $H_{[CLS]}^{(L)}$ is the embedding of the first token after L transformer layers.

2.2 Dataset

The CHB-MIT EEG database is a collection of electroencephalographic (EEG) recordings from pediatric patients with intractable epilepsy, collected at Boston Children’s Hospital, which is widely utilized in seizure research. It comprises data from 22 subjects of various ages and sexes (males and females aged 1.5-22 years), withdrawn from medication and recorded for up to multiple days. The EEG signals were recorded using the International 10-20 system, with most of them using 23 channels, sampled at 256 Hz with 16-bit resolution. In this study, data from 7 of the first patients were selected, containing a total of 32 seizure instances and approximately 442 hours of EEG recordings (23 hours after preprocessing). This selection captures a diverse range of patient profiles to evaluate each model’s ability to generalize. Data from the CHB-MIT dataset is complex and has rich temporal resolution, making it suitable for benchmarking deep learning architectures in their performance in seizure prediction.

Figure 1: EEG waveforms.

2.3 Preprocessing

The features are taken from a paper by Singh and Malhotra [7]. The preprocessing pipeline processes raw EEG data from each of the channels, extracting 30-second segments, which are a sequence consisting of ten 3-second windows for classification into preictal and interictal classes. It takes a period of 30 minutes before a seizure as the preictal period, and excludes segments 2 hours before and after seizures for the interictal period to avoid contamination. It applies a Butterworth bandpass filter (0.1- 127Hz) to remove noise, then extracts the spectral power and mean spectrum amplitude of five frequency bands (delta, theta, alpha, beta, gamma) using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Segments are then randomly shuffled and split into training (80%) and test (20%) sets. Features are then normalized before being fed into the models.

Figure 2: Different epilepsy states, along with windows used for data extraction.

2.4 Experimental setup

All models were trained using an identical preprocessing pipeline to isolate the effect of model architecture on performance. Preprocessed data is balanced to have a 1:1 ratio between the 2 labels (interictal and preictal) to have the model avoid bias and learn meaningful patterns from the data, instead of relying on learning the distribution. These methods ensure a fair and controlled benchmark and comparison of the architectures.

Data is augmented using random noise addition, scaling, and temporal shifting to help the models generalize. The models are trained via backpropagation using the RMSprop optimizer with L2 regularization to further prevent overfitting. Parameters are updated based on the binary cross-entropy loss given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{avg}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)) \quad (20)$$

A learning rate scheduler is utilized to adjust the learning rate based on validation loss. The 5 models are trained on the preprocessed data with these shared hyperparameters:

To ensure fairness, hyperparameters were tuned using a grid search strategy that minimizes validation loss. This allows each architecture to be optimized within its own structural design.

Fixed hyperparameters:

Hyperparameter	Value
Batch size	32
Epochs	50
Learning rate	0.001
Optimizer	RMSprop
Loss function	Binary cross-entropy
Learning rate scheduler	Reduce-on-plateau
Weight decay	0.0001

Table 1: Fixed hyperparameters used across all models.

Architecture-specific hyperparameters:

- **LSTM**: hidden size {64, 128, 256}, number of layers {1, 2}, dropout {0.2, 0.4, 0.5}, dense size {64, 128}
- **CNN**: number of filters {32, 64, 128}, kernel size {3, 5}, dense size {64, 128, 256}, dropout {0.2, 0.4, 0.5}

- **SNN**: hidden size {64, 128, 256}, dropout {0.2, 0.4, 0.5}, leak constant β {0.85, 0.9, 0.95}, firing threshold $\theta = 1.0$, dense size {64, 128}
- **GNN**: hidden size {64, 128, 256}, number of layers {2, 3}, dropout {0.2, 0.4, 0.5}, dense size {64, 128}
- **Transformer**: number of heads {1, 2, 4}, feedforward size {128, 256, 512}, number of layers {2, 3}, dropout {0.2, 0.4, 0.5}, dense size {64, 128}

Each model is then evaluated by their accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and ROC AUC metrics for each patient using a fixed test set, averaged across 10 trials to produce robust results.

2.5 Ethical considerations

The CHB-MIT dataset used in this study comprises anonymized EEG recordings. The dataset is publicly available and was gathered with Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval. All private health information was removed to ensure anonymity for participants. As this study involves secondary analysis of anonymized, publicly available data, no additional informed consent or ethical approval was required. All procedures in the data collection process and in this study adhere to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects.

3 Results & discussion

3.1 Results

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.909 \pm 0.009	0.936 \pm 0.008	0.905 \pm 0.010	0.964 \pm 0.005
CNN	0.888 \pm 0.004	0.931 \pm 0.005	0.882 \pm 0.004	0.934 \pm 0.002
SNN	0.897 \pm 0.012	0.940 \pm 0.021	0.890 \pm 0.015	0.958 \pm 0.008
GNN	0.924 \pm 0.010	0.923 \pm 0.008	0.924 \pm 0.013	0.959 \pm 0.006
Transformer	0.893 \pm 0.011	0.919 \pm 0.014	0.889 \pm 0.012	0.959 \pm 0.003

Table 2: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb01 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.902 ± 0.013	0.850 ± 0.020	0.905 ± 0.015	0.937 ± 0.005
CNN	0.896 ± 0.006	0.852 ± 0.022	0.899 ± 0.007	0.930 ± 0.007
SNN	0.915 ± 0.010	0.881 ± 0.000	0.917 ± 0.011	0.950 ± 0.005
GNN	0.917 ± 0.010	0.869 ± 0.023	0.920 ± 0.011	0.952 ± 0.003
Transformer	0.905 ± 0.026	0.864 ± 0.032	0.907 ± 0.029	0.935 ± 0.008

Table 3: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb02 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.832 ± 0.020	0.841 ± 0.043	0.831 ± 0.025	0.927 ± 0.008
CNN	0.805 ± 0.010	0.806 ± 0.012	0.805 ± 0.011	0.899 ± 0.004
SNN	0.826 ± 0.017	0.851 ± 0.025	0.823 ± 0.019	0.927 ± 0.008
GNN	0.894 ± 0.018	0.930 ± 0.023	0.890 ± 0.020	0.972 ± 0.004
Transformer	0.867 ± 0.020	0.867 ± 0.025	0.867 ± 0.024	0.938 ± 0.005

Table 4: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb03 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.731 ± 0.038	0.844 ± 0.056	0.729 ± 0.039	0.844 ± 0.022
CNN	0.708 ± 0.039	0.762 ± 0.026	0.707 ± 0.040	0.780 ± 0.006
SNN	0.769 ± 0.046	0.888 ± 0.023	0.768 ± 0.046	0.900 ± 0.008
GNN	0.808 ± 0.023	0.906 ± 0.039	0.806 ± 0.024	0.904 ± 0.005
Transformer	0.666 ± 0.052	0.838 ± 0.074	0.663 ± 0.053	0.828 ± 0.054

Table 5: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb04 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.613 ± 0.016	0.894 ± 0.022	0.575 ± 0.018	0.814 ± 0.010
CNN	0.644 ± 0.013	0.891 ± 0.020	0.611 ± 0.016	0.826 ± 0.011
SNN	0.753 ± 0.037	0.857 ± 0.035	0.739 ± 0.044	0.864 ± 0.011
GNN	0.659 ± 0.016	0.840 ± 0.028	0.635 ± 0.021	0.822 ± 0.008
Transformer	0.609 ± 0.038	0.927 ± 0.026	0.567 ± 0.046	0.816 ± 0.016

Table 6: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb05 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.650 ± 0.020	0.779 ± 0.026	0.633 ± 0.025	0.762 ± 0.015
CNN	0.677 ± 0.012	0.694 ± 0.034	0.675 ± 0.017	0.755 ± 0.008
SNN	0.718 ± 0.022	0.736 ± 0.063	0.716 ± 0.032	0.806 ± 0.013
GNN	0.628 ± 0.025	0.783 ± 0.055	0.608 ± 0.035	0.759 ± 0.015
Transformer	0.602 ± 0.054	0.780 ± 0.076	0.579 ± 0.069	0.746 ± 0.015

Table 7: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb06 dataset.

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC AUC
LSTM	0.808 ± 0.058	0.814 ± 0.075	0.808 ± 0.061	0.905 ± 0.017
CNN	0.829 ± 0.020	0.819 ± 0.038	0.829 ± 0.021	0.925 ± 0.005
SNN	0.840 ± 0.019	0.832 ± 0.044	0.840 ± 0.020	0.918 ± 0.005
GNN	0.838 ± 0.044	0.851 ± 0.046	0.838 ± 0.046	0.933 ± 0.009
Transformer	0.849 ± 0.040	0.805 ± 0.089	0.850 ± 0.043	0.929 ± 0.015

Table 8: Performance comparison of different model architectures on chb07 dataset.

Figure 3: Average performance metrics across all patients.

3.2 Statistical Significance Analysis

To determine whether the performance differences between model architectures were statistically significant, we used a non-parametric Friedman test applied across patients for each evaluation metric. When the Friedman test indicated significant differences, we conducted post-hoc pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests comparing the spiking neural network (SNN) against each of the other models. Holm–Bonferroni correction was applied to control for multiple comparisons.

Accuracy. The Friedman test indicated significant differences across models. Pairwise tests showed that SNNs achieved significantly higher accuracy than LSTMs, CNNs, and Transformers, but not GNNs.

Sensitivity. The Friedman test indicated significant differences across models. Pairwise tests revealed that SNNs significantly outperformed CNNs but did not perform significantly better from LSTMs, GNNs, or Transformers.

Specificity. The Friedman test indicated significant differences across models. SNNs achieved significantly higher specificity than LSTMs, CNNs, and Transformers, but not GNNs.

ROC AUC. The Friedman test indicated significant differences across models. Pairwise tests indicated that SNNs achieved significantly higher ROC AUC than LSTMs, CNNs, and Transformers, but not GNNs.

3.3 Discussion

Overall, SNNs and GNNs demonstrated the strongest and most consistent performance, while LSTMs and CNNs generally underperformed. In particular, SNNs achieved significantly higher accuracy, specificity, and ROC AUC than LSTMs, CNNs, and Transformers, indicating a strong balance between correctly classifying preictal and interictal states. These findings highlight the practical value of brain-inspired spiking dynamics for seizure prediction. GNNs performed comparably to SNNs but surpasses it in sensitivity. GNNs consistently achieved the highest average sensitivity, which is critical for clinical tasks like seizure prediction. CNNs were consistently the weakest across most metrics, likely due to their limited ability to capture complex temporal patterns. We also observe a high degree of performance variability across different patients. For instance, most models achieved high performance metrics on the chb01 and chb02 datasets, while performance dropped substantially for chb05 and chb06. This suggests that patient-specific models or transfer learning approaches may be necessary for clinical viability for EEG seizure prediction.

4 Conclusion & Future Work

This study conducted a systematic evaluation of five deep learning architectures for EEG-based seizure prediction. The results show that Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) reliably outperform CNNs, LSTMs, and Transformers across most metrics, though their performance is comparable to GNNs. This supports the idea that brain-inspired models are a promising direction for advancing seizure prediction systems. However, their performance has not yet surpassed that of the best-performing conventional models. GNNs, while not significantly better than SNNs overall, achieved the highest average sensitivity, underscoring their potential in clinical contexts where minimizing false negatives is critical. CNNs and LSTMs, though effective, generally lagged behind in this benchmark. The significant patient-level variability highlights the importance of developing models that generalize across

individuals or adapt to specific patients. Future work should focus on refining SNN architectures and training methods, while also exploring their computational efficiency, to further establish them as biologically plausible and clinically viable tools for seizure prediction.

5 Acknowledgements

The author used publicly available data from the CHB-MIT Scalp EEG Database (<https://physionet.org/content/chbmit/1.0.0/>)

6 Conflicts of interest

The author declares that there are no conflict of interests related to this work.

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